

ORGANIZATION OF EFFECTIVE MANAGEMENT AT WHOLESALE AND RETAIL TRADE ENTERPRISES.

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8093012>

Annotation. This article discusses the problems of providing a system professional management at the enterprise. At present, the question of having an objective, reliable and operational assessment of management activities, as a result of which the issues of management efficiency of trade enterprises are resolved.

Key words: management, methodological approach, organization efficiency, trading company management practices.

The rapid changes that are characteristic of the present instability and increased competition in the domestic market determine the need for a balanced and professional approach to management of an enterprise, regardless of its scale and scope of activity.

The most relevant is this approach to the organization of the management system for enterprise is in conditions of extremely limited necessary resources. At the same time, along with the problems of providing a system professional management at the enterprise, the question of having an objective, reliable and

operational assessment of management activities. Modern management science has accumulated a significant set of methods for determining the effectiveness of the organization, but, so far, there is no single methodological approach. This is due to the multidimensionality of this category. Efficiency is an integral and structured characteristic of an organization that comprehensively reflects the success of an organization in accordance with its mission, goals and objectives. Managers during the analysis of the management activities of enterprises predominantly use calculation methods and indicators that describe the organizational features of enterprises. The advantage of this approach is a large number of currently known indicators, formulas for their calculation. Such methods also have disadvantages, for example, many indicators are a trade secret, some integral evaluation indicators have insufficient semantic meaning and are not always practically applicable. To build effective enterprise management, it is necessary to solve the following tasks:

1. Analysis of the effectiveness of management in a trade organization based on the materials of the enterprise.
2. Identification of existing problems and the choice of methods for their elimination.
3. Development of recommendations for improving management efficiency.

The development of management is always based on specific potential, which is the source and guarantor of development. An analysis of the practice of managing trading companies makes it possible to

conclusion about the existence of new trends in management, the hallmark of which can be considered the transition to more flexible and efficient mechanisms and management tools.

There is a rearrangement of priorities in management, which radically changes both the ideology of management and the basic functions of management.

A modern trading company is characterized by a wide range of goods and a large number of suppliers. These conditions require accuracy, high speed of information flow, fast making decisions.

From the standpoint of a systematic approach, the organization can be considered as an open system, the characteristic features of which are determined by the interaction of its elements (internal environment) and are inextricably linked with the external environment of direct and indirect influence. A service sector enterprise (in particular, trade) as an object of management

can be viewed through a set of trade and technological processes, i.e. a complex of trade (commercial) and technological operations, sequentially interconnected, the purpose of which is to bring goods in a wide range and of good quality to consumers with the least labor and time costs and is the final stage of the entire process of product distribution.

To ensure the effectiveness of management, it is necessary to take into account all factors: external and internal, and from them to single out the main and determining factors.

The action of factors leads to a change in efficiency through the dynamics

the costs of achieving the result (their size, structure, etc.) and/or changing conditions, opportunities for obtaining an effect. At the same time, the factors having a direct impact on the change in economic efficiency, leading to changes in the control object (enterprise), require adequate response of the control system and thus affect management efficiency. Accordingly, the factors directly affecting the effectiveness of the management system, determine the nature managerial impact on the control object, which causes a change economic efficiency. So, when considering the factors of performance efficiency, one cannot say that management factors affect only the management system, and it is necessary to analyze their complex impact on the efficiency of the entire activity of a trading enterprise.

All factors that affect the organization and its effectiveness activities relate to the external or internal environment of its functioning and development.

External effectiveness of management and activities in general determined by the ability of the management system to take into account and analyze external factors, use development opportunities and their strengths side, mitigate threats, strengthen weaknesses, i.e. capabilities management of the enterprise to such methods of environmental analysis as STEP and SWOT.

At the same time, an organization can significantly influence the nature and the content of interaction with the factors of the immediate environment (environment of direct impact), which means creating additional opportunities for yourself and preventing the emergence of threats to its activities

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